

Anodic mediated synthesis and antifungal study of bis-1,3,4-oxadiazoles

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Abstract : A novel, facile and eco-compatible electrochemical synthesis of substituted bis-1,3,4-oxadiazoles have been carried out at platinum electrode via controlled potential electrocyclization of methylenediacylthiosemicarbazones in the presence of acetonitrile as non-aqueous solvent and LiClO₄ as supporting electrolyte. The reaction products were characterized by spectroscopic methods and mechanism was deduced from cyclic voltammetry. The synthesized compounds were screened for their antifungal activity against *Candida albicans*, *Alternaria solani*, *Aspergillus niger* and results have been compared with the standard antifungal drug Griseofulvin. Excellent yields with high atom economy, shortest reaction time and easy work-up are attractive features in context to green chemistry.

Keywords : Electrochemical synthesis, environmentally benign, bis-oxadiazoles, controlled potential electrolysis, green chemistry.

Introduction

1,3,4-Oxadiazole derivatives are well known to have a wide range of biological activities such as antibacterial¹, anti HIV¹, antifungal², genotoxic², antituberculosis³, virucidal⁴, antimalarial⁵, insecticidal⁶, herbicidal⁷, analgesic⁸, anti-inflammatory⁹, muscle relaxants¹⁰, anti-convulsant¹¹, sedative, hypnotic¹², anticancer¹³ and lipid peroxidation inhibitor¹⁴.

The utility, activity² and functions of bis-1,3,4-oxadiazoles are more important than 1,3,4-oxadiazoles. Some bis-oxadiazoles show nematocidal, insecticidal and herbicidal activities¹⁵. Bis-mercapto-1,3,4-oxadiazoles were used as active substance to control *Meloidogyne incognita* in tomato¹⁶. The benzyl substitution in compounds leads not only to an increase in the antimicrobial activity but the length of the alkane (No. of *n*) is also an important factor for the activity. In the present investigation, a series of substituted bis-1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives were synthesized as potential antifungal agents.

It seems that this electrochemical procedure will emerge as new tool where the special advantages of the electrochemistry such as energy specificity, chemical selectivity

and specific activation of small molecules can be applied without toxic reagents and solvents. As part of our programme for the development of simple, facile, environmentally benign protocol for the synthesis of biodynamic heterocyclic compounds, we describe here oxidative electrocyclization of different methylenediacylthiosemicarbazides into 5,5'-(amino)substituted-bis-1,3,4-oxadiazoles and evaluation of their antifungal activity.

Results and discussion

Conventional protocol include bromine oxidation of semicarbazide derivative and the cyclodesulfurization of acylthiosemicarbazide derivatives in solution using I₂/NaOH or 1,3-dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (DCC)¹⁷⁻¹⁹, as well as mercury(II) acetate (Hg(OAc)₂) or yellow mercury(II) oxide HgO²⁰⁻²³.

These methods have many drawbacks, many of them usually carried out in different synthetic steps that require very dangerous reagents such as bromine or full equivalent of Hg^{II} and produce undesirable mercury byproducts which must be removed and properly disposed off after the reaction is completed. Not only han-

ding of these reagents is difficult but also very hazardous to the environment. From the first step to last step of the reaction including extraction and purification of the product demands great precautions.

With increasing public concern over environmental degradation, use of electrochemical technology can provide a valuable alternative to the conventional reagents for fine chemical synthesis. Due to the electron transfer between an electrode and the substrate molecules the formation of highly reactive intermediates are achieved under mild condition, avoiding acid and bases as reducing or oxidizing agent and related waste by-products.

The objective of our research programme is to find a new environmentally benign preparation of bis-1,3,4-

oxadiazoles, in which the use of toxic reagents could be minimized. Keeping that objective in mind, we synthesized some 5,5'-(amino)substituted-bis-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (**6a-g**) by anodic mediated cyclization of methylenediacylthiosemicarbazone (**5a-g**) at the platinum electrode. This electrochemical cyclization gave the oxadiazoles (**6a-g**) without requirement of any hazardous reagents. Acetonitrile/acetic acid was used as a solvent and lithium perchlorate (LiClO_4) as supporting electrolyte which can be handled easily without major precautions.

Electrochemical study of methylenediacylthiosemicarbazone (5a) :

Cyclic voltammograms of methylenediacylthiosemicarbazone (**5a**) has been studied in acetonitrile solution

containing 0.1 M lithium perchlorate are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammogram of **5a** in 0.1 M LiClO₄ at platinum electrode (area 1 × 1 cm²) at scan rate of 100 mV s⁻¹, counter electrode; platinum mesh, reference electrode; Ag/AgCl, *t* = 25 ± 1 °C. The corresponding CV exhibit one anodic peak at 1.31 V. This peak indicates electrooxidative cyclization of methylenediacylthiosemicarbazone (**5a**).

Experimental

Instruments :

The electrochemical synthesis was performed in 250 mL three-electrode cell assembly with platinum plate (flattened sheet with dimension of 1.0 cm × 1.0 cm), counter electrode and saturated calomel electrode as reference electrode. Cyclic voltammetry was performed using ALSCH instruments electrochemical analyzer Model 600A.

¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectra were obtained on Bruker DRX (400 MHz) spectrometer in CDCl₃ and TMS as an internal standards (Chemical shifts in δ ppm). IR spectra were registered with a Shimadzu 8201 PC spectrometer in KBr pellets. Mass spectra were obtained by EI method with Shimadzu GCMS-QP5050A. The elemental analysis was done on Elemental Vario EL III. Column chromatography was carried out by using Merck silica gel 60. The purity of the synthesized compounds were confirmed by TLC on pre-coated silica gel plates in various solvent system using iodine vapors and UV light as detecting agents.

Chemicals and reagents :

All the chemicals used were of synthetic and AR grade and was procured from Agros-Organics, USA, S. D. Fine

Chem. Ltd., Mumbai and Merck, Mumbai, India. These chemicals were used without further purification. All experiments were carried out at room temperature.

Electroorganic synthesis of **6a-g** controlled potential electrolysis (ECE) :

Acylhydrazine (**3**) was prepared by dissolving hydrazine hydrate (**2**) and diethyl ester (**1**) (diethyl malonate) in 2 : 1 ratio with continuous stirring. The mixture was left overnight which evolved a solid product **3**. Equimolar amount of acylhydrazine (**3**) and phenylisothiocyanate (**4**) mixed in a small beaker with continuous stirring evolved a solid product methylenediacylthiosemicarbazone (**5**) which was used as initial compound for the electrolysis.

Electrolysis :

In a typical procedure, 100 mL mixture of acetonitrile containing methylenediacylthiosemicarbazone (0.271 g, 1.0 mmol) and supporting electrolyte LiClO₄ (0.16 g, 1.0 mmol) were added to the electrolytic cell. Preparative scale controlled potential electrolysis²⁴⁻³² were carried out at corresponding oxidation potentials of the substrates and were completed in 3 to 4 h until no oxidation product was seen to diffuse in the bulk. Magnetic stirrer was used for the proper mixing of reaction mixture. All the products were solid, colored and entirely different from the starting compound. The current potential data was recorded with the help of potentiostat at the interval of 15 min as depicted in Table 1.

The electrocyclization of **5a** was carried out in acetonitrile at constant potential of 1.31 V using LiClO₄ as supporting electrolyte. The electricity used for the electrolysis was very small as compared to other conventional methods. Progress of reaction was monitored by TLC. When the reaction was completed, supporting electrolyte was removed by silica gel column chromatography. The products were isolated by silica gel column chromatography (CHCl₃ : H₂O, 1 : 1 v/v).

Screening of antifungal activity :

Antifungal activities were studied against fungal strain *Candida albicans*, *Alternaria solani* and *Aspergillus niger* at 10, 100, 1000 ppm concentration using commercial fungicide, Griseofulvin as standards by agar growth technique³³. The numbers of replicate assays in each were three, and six replicate controls were used and no re-

Table 1. Current-potential and yield data of bis-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (6a-g)

Sl. no.	Substrate	N	R	Product	Time (min)	Applied potential ^a (V)	Current (A)	Yield ^b (%)
1	5a	1	C ₆ H ₅ -	6a	190	1.31	0.60	81
2	5b	1	2-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄ -	6b	200	1.42	0.80	89
3	5c	1	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄ -	6c	200	1.45	0.80	90
4	5d	1	2-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ -	6d	180	1.35	0.70	91
5	5e	1	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -	6e	230	1.38	0.90	72
6	5f	1	3-ClC ₆ H ₄ -	6f	210	1.32	0.60	73
7	5g	1	C ₁₀ H ₇ -	6g	220	1.39	0.75	79

^aApplied potential of the substrates. ^bYield of the product.

Fig. 2. IR spectra of the representative compound 6a.

markable morphological changes were observed in the developing fungi. The test fungi were inoculated in the centre of the petridishes and incubated at 28 ± 1 °C for 96 h. After this time the percent inhibition of the mycelia growth compared with that in control dishes was recorded. The antifungal activity of the compounds varied upon type and position of the substituent at 2 position of oxadiazole ring.

The screening results showed that compounds **6b**, **6c**

and **6f** showed efficient antifungal activity against the test fungi (Table 2). This demonstrates that the presence of hydrophilic group on aryl amino ring (attached with 2 position of oxadiazole) enhances the antifungal activity while presence of hydrophobic group at same position decreases the antifungal activity.

Characterization of the products :

5,5'-Methylenebis[*N*-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-amine] (**6a**) : ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 6.46–7.01 (10H, m, Ar-H),

Table 2. Antifungal screening results of the products 6a-g^d

Compd.	<i>Candida albicans</i>			<i>Alternaria solani</i>			<i>Aspergillus niger</i>		
	1000	100	10	1000	100	10	1000	100	10
	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm
6a	66	43	22	65	41	19	66	42	21
6b	84	63	43	85	63	44	83	61	42
6c	90	71	52	90	72	53	89	70	50
6d	68	48	26	69	49	27	67	47	25
6e	77	55	28	78	55	29	76	53	27
6f	88	67	46	89	68	47	88	68	45
6g	51	26	10	52	27	11	50	25	9
Griseofulvin	100	81	63	100	82	65	100	81	64

^aAverage inhibition of fungal growth (%) at stated concentration (mg/L⁻¹).

3.98 (1H, s, NH), 3.98 (1H, s, NH), 3.81 (2H, m, CH₂); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 115–146.7 (Ar C–C), 29.7 (CH₂); IR (KBr) : 3421 (N–H), 2921 (C–H, aromatic), 1594 (C=N), 1242, 1028 (C–O–C) (Found : C, 61.12; H, 4.08; N, 25.29. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₄N₆O₂ : C, 61.05; H, 4.18; N, 25.20%); EIMS (*m/z*) 334 [M⁺].

5,5'-Methylenebis[*N*-(2-methoxyphenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-amine] (6b) : ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 6.35–6.57 (8H, m, Ar-H), 3.98 (1H, s, NH), 3.98 (1H, s, NH), 3.81 (2H, m, CH₂), 3.73 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.73 (3H, s, OCH₃); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 116–148.6 (Ar C–C), 29.7 (CH₂), 56.0 (OCH₃); IR (KBr) : 3414 (N–H), 2924 (C–H, aromatic), 1599 (C=N), 1256, 1026 (C–O–C) (Found : C, 57.77; H, 4.58; N, 21.45. Calcd. for C₁₉H₁₈N₆O₄ : C, 57.83; H, 4.53; N, 21.38%); EIMS (*m/z*) 394 [M⁺].

5,5'-Methylenebis[*N*-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-amine] (6c) : ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 6.35–6.52 (8H, m, Ar-H), 3.98 (1H, s, NH), 3.98 (1H, s, NH), 2.35 (2H, m, CH₂), 2.53 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.81 (3H, s, CH₃); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 114.9–152.0 (Ar C–C), 29.7 (CH₂), 56.0 (OCH₃); IR (KBr) : 3359 (N–H), 2924, 2839 (C–H, aromatic), 1614 (C=N), 1256, 1026 (C–O–C) (Found : C, 57.87; H, 4.58; N, 21.37. Calcd. for C₁₉H₁₈N₆O₄ : C, 57.83; H, 4.49; N, 21.46%); EIMS (*m/z*) 394 [M⁺].

5,5'-Methylenebis[*N*-(2-methylphenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-amine] (6d) : ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 6.32–6.82 (8H, m, Ar-H), 3.98 (1H, s, NH), 3.98 (1H, s, NH), 2.35 (2H, m, CH₂), 3.73 (3H, s, OCH₃), 2.53 (3H,

s, CH₃); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 115.0–130.0 (Ar C–C), 29.7 (CH₂), 12.1 (CH₃); IR (KBr) : 3359 (N–H), 2924, 2839 (C–H, aromatic), 1614 (C=N), 1256, 1026 (C–O–C) (Found : C, 62.77; H, 5.13; N, 23.15. Calcd. for C₁₉H₁₈N₆O₂ : C, 62.89; H, 5.06; N, 23.21%); EIMS (*m/z*) 362 [M⁺].

5,5'-Methylenebis[*N*-(3-nitrophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-amine] (6e) : ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 6.85–7.55 (8H, m, Ar-H), 3.98 (1H, s, NH), 3.81 (2H, m, CH₂); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 116.2–150.2 (Ar C–C), 29.7 (CH₂); IR (KBr) : 3354 (N–H), 2923, 2838 (C–H, aromatic), 1614 (C=N), 1259, 1031 (C–O–C) (Found : C, 48.07; H, 2.79; N, 26.46. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₂N₈O₆ : C, 48.14; H, 2.88; N, 26.39%); EIMS (*m/z*) 424 [M⁺].

5,5'-Methylenebis[*N*-(3-chlorophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-amine] (6f) : ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 6.34–6.95 (8H, m, Ar-H), 3.98 (1H, s, NH), 3.81 (2H, m, CH₂); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 113.2–134.6 (Ar C–C), 29.7 (CH₂); IR (KBr) : 3355 (N–H), 2921, 2838 (C–H, aromatic), 1620 (C=N), 1260, 1026 (C–O–C) (Found : C, 50.47; H, 3.11; N, 20.67. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₂Cl₂N₆O₂ : C, 50.59; H, 3.05; N, 20.79%); EIMS (*m/z*) 342 [M⁺].

5,5'-Methylenebis[*N*-naphthylphenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-amine] (6g) : ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 6.55–7.66 (14H, m, Ar-H), 3.98 (1H, s, NH), 3.81 (2H, m, CH₂); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 109.4–142.0 (Ar C–C), 29.7 (CH₂); IR (KBr) : 3359 (N–H), 2922, 2839 (C–H, aromatic), 1617 (C=N), 1258, 1030 (C–O–C) (Found : C, 69.07; H, 4.18; N, 19.29. Calcd. for C₂₅H₁₈N₆O₂ : C, 69.14; H, 4.12; N, 19.36%); EIMS (*m/z*) 434 [M⁺].

Conclusion :

A new, facile and efficient methodology for eco-compatible preparation of substituted bis-1,3,4-oxadiazoles via one pot controlled potential anodic mediated electrocyclization of methylenediacylthiosemicarbazones has been developed in our laboratory. All the synthesised compounds exhibited significant antifungal activity against the tested fungi. It is evident from the antifungal screening results that antifungal activity of the compounds varied upon type and position of the substituents at 2 position of oxadiazole moiety. The mildness of the electrooxidation, experimental simplicity, compatibility with various functional groups, excellent product yield, shorter reaction time, and the easy work-up procedure make this approach more attractive in synthesizing a variety of such derivatives.

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